

Transannular Electronic Interactions between Nonconjugated Groups of 1, 6-Dimethylenecyclodecane and its Synthesis

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An interesting ten-membered medium-sized ring compound, 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane is synthesized, and its ultraviolet absorption spectrum in ethanol is studied. The compound exhibits an unusual absorption band at a wave-length of 256nm, and has a molar extinction coefficient of 500 liter mole⁻¹cm⁻¹. The origin of this transition and its assignment are discussed from the standpoint of the transannular double bond-double bond interaction. This is an interesting consequence of the stereochemistry of the ten-membered ring.

ONE of the advantages of the molecular orbital theory is that it readily accounts for electronic interactions between certain double bond groups which are not conjugated in the classical sense. The purpose of this paper is to describe the synthesis of 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane, and to discuss the electronic interactions between transannular nonconjugated two C=C groups in this compound.

By using naphthalene I as the starting material, a medium-sized ring compound 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane V was prepared.

Naphthalene I was first reduced to 9, 10-octalin II by lithium metal in *n*-propylamine¹. The peroxide oxidation of the 9, 10-octalin II produced 9, 10 decalindiol III which was further oxidized to 1, 6-cyclodecanedione IV by lead tetraacetate². The dione was next converted to 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane by means of Wittig reaction^{3,4}. The sequence of reactions is represented in Fig. 1.

Transannular Interaction :

The visible and ultraviolet spectra of 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane have been measured, and the

Fig. 1. Reactions sequence

cyclodecane V was prepared. Naphthalene was first reduced to 9, 10-octalin II by lithium metal in *n*-propylamine¹. The peroxide oxidation of the 9, 10-octalin II produced 9, 10 decalindiol III which was further oxidized to 1, 6-cyclodecanedione IV by lead tetraacetate². The dione was next converted to 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane by means of Wittig reaction^{3,4}. The sequence of reactions is represented in Fig. 1.

The visible and ultraviolet spectra of 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane have been measured, and the compound exhibits an unusual absorption band at 256 nm with a molar extinction coefficient of 500. Similar bands have been observed in the spectra of

ten membered cyclic systems containing nonconjugated chromophores (Table 1) and have been attributed to transannular electronic interactions^{4,6,7,8}.

TABLE I - COMPARISON OF SPECTRAL DATA FOR 1, 6-DIMETHYLENOCYCLODECANE AND RELATED COMPOUNDS^{4,6,7,8}

Compound	Solvent	λ_{\max} , nm	ϵ_{\max}
1, 6-Dimethylenecyclodecane	Ethanol	256	500
Cyclodec-5-en-1-one ⁶	Ethanol	258	472
1, 6-Cyclodecanedione ⁶	Ethanol	287	35
1-Methyl-1-azacyclodecane-6-one ^{7,8}	Diethyl ether	221	5600
1-Thiacyclooctane-5-one ⁷	—	238	2535

In the case of 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane, because of the flexibility and the puckering of the ten-membered ring, the nonconjugated C=C chromophores can come closer to each other, and assume a S.cis-butadiene type of configuration. This permits the orientation of the *p*-orbitals of both the ethylenic groups to be parallel to each other, and thus permit orbital overlap as shown in Fig. 2. This has been

Fig. 2. *p*-orbital parallel overlap

confirmed by model construction of 1, 6-dimethylenecyclodecane.

Such an orbital overlap gives rise to bonding and antibonding π molecular orbitals which encompass both the chromophores. The relatively low intensity of the 256 nm band can then be assigned to the π - π^* transition.

Transannular Interactions in Other Related Compounds:

In order to detect possible transannular interactions between C=C and C=O groups when these groups are located opposite to each other in a ten-membered ring compound, cyclodec-5-en-1-one, an anomalous ultraviolet maximum at 258 nm and molar extinction coefficient of 472 have been determined⁶. In another ten-membered ring, 1-methyl-1-azacyclodecane-6-one, an anomalous ultraviolet maximum at 221 nm and molar extinction coefficient of 5600 reflected strong interaction between the C=O group and the nitrogen atom^{7,8}.

Experimental

9, 10-Octalin² II:

51.2g of naphthalene (0.4 mole) were dissolved in 1000 ml of *n*-propylamine in a three-necked flask under nitrogen atmosphere. Then 33.2g (4.8 moles) of lithium were added in small pieces at room temperature with vigorous stirring. After 20 hrs., the solution was decomposed by the cautious addition of solid ammonium chloride till the solution became colorless. Water was added dropwise to the residue with external cooling. The oily organic layer was extracted with ether and separated from the aqueous layer. Ether was stripped off and the product was isolated by high vacuum distillation. 42.3g of colorless oil distilling at 60° and 0.1 mm pressure of Hg, were obtained. The yield was 89%.

9, 10-Decalindiol³ III:

213 ml of 90% formic acid and 79 ml of 27% hydrogen peroxide were placed in a three-necked flask. 74 g of 9, 10-octalin were added during a 30 min. period. This was done under nitrogen atmosphere with stirring at 45° ± 3°. The solution was warmed and stirred for six additional hours. The product was diluted to 500 ml with water, and 150g of sodium chloride were added and well mixed, giving oil which soon solidified in the ice chest. The product was collected, washed with water, and dried as a hydroxy formoxy compound. The hydroxy formoxy compound was hydrolysed by adding 80g of sodium hydroxide in 150 ml of ice-cold water. It was then stirred for one-half hour at room temperature, and one hour at 75° to 80°. The mixture was diluted with 375 ml of water, a crystalline product was filtered after several hours, washed with water and dried. It was recrystallized from aqueous acetone. The net yield was 80%, or 54g. The melting point was determined to be 89–90°.

Cyclodecanedione³ IV

25g. of the molten dihydroxy compound III were added to 200 ml. of dry benzene. The mixture was treated with 74g of lead tetra-acetate at room temperature during one and one-half hours. It was stirred for 2½ hrs. more and then refluxed for 30 mins. at 60°. The excess lead tetra-acetate was filtered and washed with 4 × 17 ml of benzene. The solvent was distilled under a slight vacuum, yielded 1, 6-cyclodecanedione which was then recrystallized

from petroleum ether. The yield was 87%, or 18g. The melting point was determined to be 59°.

Dimethylenecyclodecane^{2, 4 V}

Methyltriphenyl-phosphonium bromide (0.012 mole) and phenyl-lithium solution (0.013 mole) were placed in a nitrogen-filled three-necked flask. After the reaction mixture had been stirred vigorously for three and one-half hours, a solution of 2g (0.0125 mole) of cyclodecanedione in 5 ml of anhydrous ethyl ether was added slowly by drops. After 24 hrs the ether was removed by distillation, 20 ml of anhydrous glyme (ethylene glycol) was added, and the mixture was stirred and heated at 80°-90° for 5 hrs. The mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtered cakes were washed with 2 × 20 portions of pentane, and the pentane washings were used to extract the filtrate which had been diluted with water. The combined pentane extracts were washed with 3 × 10 ml portions of water to remove all glyme (ethylene glycol). The total pentane solution was dried over magnesium sulfate and the solvent removed by distillation. The residue was distilled at reduced pressure to yield 1.7g of dimethylene-

cyclodecane. The yield was 83%. Boiling point was 110°-112° at about 25 mm pressure. The refractive index was $n_D^{25} = 1.5503$. Vapor phase chromatography indicated a purity of 99.99%. Infrared absorption for carbon carbon double bonds was at 1630 cm^{-1} . Ultraviolet absorption was at 256 nm. Carbon hydrogen analysis, calculated for $C_{12}H_{20}$: C, 87.8; H, 12.2. Found: C, 87.12; H, 12.19.

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